

The Impact Of Psychological Disability On Marriage And Divorce In Islamic Jurisprudence

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Abstract

Mental health in the concept of Islam has multiple aspects that include the dimensions of the human soul spiritually, psychologically, socially and physically. Each of those aspects has its importance and impact on the health and safety of the soul. The absence or contradiction of one of the said aspects, especially the spiritual aspect, prevents the individual from enjoying a balanced personality, and makes him more vulnerable to psychological disorders. Therefore, Islam stipulated relevant rulings foreach of those aspects. The issue of marriage and divorce is very important, so I thought that I should research this topic for people with psychological disabilities that Allah the Almighty has afflicted them therewith, so that they may be aware of their actions.

Introduction

Allah the Almighty created good and evil and the darkness and the light, to be identified by their opposites. For instance, people's actions make us know the value of goodness and darkness makes us know the value of the light. Therefore, Allah, the Almighty reminds us of this great cause, saying in His Holy Quran:

“Tell me! If Allâh made the day continuous for you till the Day of Resurrection, which ilâh (god) besides Allâh could bring you night wherein you rest? Will you not then see? It is out of His Mercy that He has made for you the night and the day that you may rest therein (i.e. during the night) and that you may seek of His Bounty (i.e. during the day) - and in order that you may be grateful”

”[Alqasas] stories: verses 72 - 73]

It is a wisdom that our Lord “Allah, the Almighty” teaches us in order for us to submit to Him in wisdom that we do not know and do not realize. Glory be to Him. Allah, the Almighty created the healthy people and created the sick people - whom we have come to call the handicapped or the persons with special needs - so that we know the value of health, which is a crown on the heads of the healthy people that only the sick know its value , but Allah, the Almighty reminds us of the precious health when we see those patients in order to thank Allah, the Almighty for His blessings and to pray for those sick people whom are afflicted with diseases, so that we are not among the unfair ones who do not feel the blessings they own, and those to whom the Prophet (PBUH) referred to in what Ibn Abbas, may Allah, the Almighty be pleased with him, said: “There are two blessings in which many people waste, health and free time.” (1)

1-The concept of psychological disorder according to Muslim scholars:

The Islamic perspective on the subject of mental health is concerned with the spiritual factors, unlike modern psychologists who neglect such factors in their study of personality and mental health. Psychologists define mental health as: the emotional and social maturity, an individual's compatibility with himself and the world around him, and his ability to assume life responsibilities and face the challenges, and the individual's acceptance of his life and feeling content and happiness therewith.(2) The exclusion of the role of religion in the individual's enjoyment of mental health and instilling safety and tranquility in the souls is clear in their definition of mental health; whereas, mental health was defined out of the Islamic perspective as: achieving a balance between satisfying the needs of the soul and the needs of the body and achieving environmental and social compatibility in accordance with “Shariah”jurisprudence regulations.(3)

Mental health in the concept of the Islam has multiple aspects that include the dimensions of the human soul spiritually, psychologically, socially and physically, and each of these aspects has its importance and impact on the health and safety of the soul, and the absence or contradiction of one of such aspects, especially the spiritual

aspect, prevents the individual from enjoying a balanced personality, and makes him more vulnerable to mental disorders. (4)

Mental disorders in the concept of religion are of two types: apparent deviations and internal deviations. The first type includes: psychological and mental diseases, and the second type includes: bad thoughts, feelings and emotions; they are what Islamic scholars call the inner sin or diseases of the heart (5) and examples of them are as follows: hypocrisy, arrogance, envy, mistrust and the like. However, we do not find such internal disturbances in clinical psychology; because a person's inflection with them does not denote that the person is a patient according to the medical standard, but he is considered a patient according to the Islamic standard and is in need of treatment (6)

Mental disorders can also be classified into:

- Minor mental disorders or neurotic disorders (7).
- Major mental disorders or psychotic disorders. (8)

2- Marriage of the psychologically troubled person:

The jurists unanimously agreed on the invalidity of every behavior of the insane, because the insane has no guardianship over himself (9), including his marriage under the guardian of himself, so his action is not considered, and the guardianship of marriage is transferred to someone else. However, the jurists differed in the ruling on his marriage on two opinions:

The first opinion: The Hanafis (10), the Malikis (11) and the Hanbalis (12) are of the opinion that it is permissible for the guardian to marry an insane man and an insane woman; because they did not consider reason or puberty as a condition for the validity of the marriage (13), and they argued (14) that the marriage of an insane person has multiple interests; including: repelling the harm of lust, repelling immorality and embracing chastity, as well as collecting dowry and alimony.

The second opinion: The Shafis are of the opinion (15) that an insane man or woman should not be married, unless there is an interest and a need for that; for example, in marriage, there is a reason for the cessation of insanity, because in marriage there is expense for the insane which is represented in a dowry and alimony; so the adult insane person should not be married unless there is an instant need thereof, for instance, he has a desire for women embodied in his attachment to them and seeking them, or that he needs someone to serve him, and he does not find in his "mahrams" (closest kinship) someone to serve him, so he gets married if he reaches puberty. As for the young insane, there is no need to marry him because he does not need to marry.

The safest opinion - and Allah knows best - is to take the Shafi'i opinion in regard to the interest or need of the marriage of the insane person, such as expecting recovery or his assistance in his livelihood, especially we know that insanity and some mental diseases are transmitted through inheritance. This is a condition of protecting society from the spread of infirmities in it and Sharia always urges the choice of the husband and the wife who are healthy and void of diseases (16).

Accordingly, it is permissible for a mentally disturbed person to be married off, if there is an interest in his marriage, regardless of the type of psychological disorder he suffers from, as long as this disorder does not affect the disturbed person's performance of his social, family, material, and marital responsibilities (17). The argument for this is that mental disease does not deprive the person of the desire for marriage, and if his guardian does not marry him, (18) it will harm him (19) (and the harm will be removed through marriage). We must know that many psychologically disturbed people can marry without problems, but this requires consulting a psychiatrist before embarking on marriage to know the possibility of the intended marriage without complacency. As the possibility of the inheritance of one of the children of the psychological disease or the emergence of psychological disorders in children as a result of the errors of upbringing and handling on the part of the mentally ill parents remains present (20) and the same applies to the mentally ill woman, so it is permissible to marry her if her condition is stable and the husband is satisfied with her, according to the agreement of the jurists that the guardian may marry the insane woman, whether young or old (21).

However, there are required conditions for the marriage of the mentally disturbed person. (22)

As a matter of fact, psychiatry believes that giving a general opinion about the possibility of marrying a psychiatric patient remains difficult. As psychological disorders vary in their severity and the psychological and social disability they cause. Most personality disorders, including: some behavioral disorders, neurological diseases, and some mild, intermittent, and curable mental diseases and their stability allow their owners to marry due to the stability and the balance of the behaviors of those inflicted with the said diseases. On the other hand, there are some other mental diseases that marriage is not preferred therewith, such as: some severe mental disorders such as deteriorating schizophrenia and severe chronic psychotic affective disorder, as well as cases of severe mental retardation or bad personality disorders such as psychopathy (aggressive personality) (23).

In cases of advanced schizophrenia, for example, as doctors say, in order to make the appropriate decision about marriage or not, it is necessary to pay attention to the following most important matters:

A- Knowing that marriage does not cure disease, but may help in healing if it is a successful marriage and may aggravate patient's condition if it is not a successful marriage. As marriage may add burdens and responsibilities on the patient that he is unable to bear. In this case, this may lead to relapse of the patient.

B- Awareness of the other party in the future married life of the patient's condition, his approval therewith, his complete readiness to coexist with it, and his awareness of his role in treatment.

C- The goal of the psychiatric patient's family is to marry him off to make him happy, not to get rid of the burden of taking care of him and assigning another party to do so.

The same applies to people with neurotic disorders that are less severe than psychotic disorders; such as obsessive-compulsive disorder, phobias, depression and the like. Those patients are also permissible to marry if the woman and her guardians are satisfied with such marriage, and the disordered person does not constitute danger in most cases (24). Actually, psychological disorders vary in their severity and symptoms. This is why we find the neurotic patient is less dangerous to married life than the psychotic patient. However, this does not negate the effect of this type of psychiatric disturbance on marital life (25)

In conclusion, I can say that:

- Out of the psychiatric point of opinion, there is no problem with the marriage of the psychologically disturbed person as long as the other party is aware of his condition. The possibility of such marriage is decided by the psychiatrist supervising the patient's mental state. The decision to marry or not is a joint decision among the patient's family, doctor and life partner.

- It is permissible to marry the psychologically disturbed person from the legal side, regardless of the type of his disorder, even if he is one of those whose awareness is always absent, provided that he is married by his guardian; and his fiancée was aware of his disease before marriage, and that his marriage should not harm him or his wife after the doctor supervising the patient's condition decided the same.

3: The impact of psychological disorders on divorce rulings:

In this topic, I will review the impact of psychological disorders on the rulings of divorce, and then I will discuss the issue of divorce in two types of the psychologically disturbed people; divorce of the person troubled by obsessive-compulsive disorder, and then divorce by the psychotic troubled person.

First: Divorce by the person troubled by obsessive-compulsive disorder:

The psychologically disturbed person has three cases in divorce:

The first case: that the obsessive person is afflicted with obsession in a way other than marriage and divorce, such as obsession in purification and prayer. (26)

The second case: That his obsession is in the matter of marriage, and has gotten him to the point of insanity (27), then such a divorce does not count, because he is considered not obligated, and the proof is the saying of Prophet Mohammed (PBUH): (The pen has been lifted from three: from the sleeper until he wakes up, from the boy until he reaches puberty, and from the insane until he becomes sane) (28). So, every disease dominating the mind of its owner, including the obsessive person, the insane and the imbecile, their divorce does not count according to the opinion of Imam Al-Shafi'i. (29).

The third case: That he was obsessed with the matter of marriage and did not reach the point of insanity, and this obsessive person has two situations, they are as follows:

The first situation: If the patient tells himself about the divorce or has the intention of divorce without uttering it, then his divorce does not count according to the majority of jurists (30).

The second situation: That the obsessed person utters the word "divorce" in order to be relieved of obsession, and the jurists have two opinions on this issue:

The first opinion: Divorce of the obsessive person does not count even if it is uttered, and this is the opinion of the Hanafis (31), and the Malikis (32), and Ibn Al-Qayyim (33), and Ibn Uthaymeen (34), and accordingly, the Standing Committee issued a fatwa thereof (35).

The second opinion: Divorce of the obsessive person counts, and it is the Shafi'i school (36), and the Hanbalis (37).

Evidence of the owners of the first opinion: Evidence including:

1 – It is narrated by Aisha, May Allah be pleased with her, she said: Prophet Mohammed (PBUH), said: "There is no divorce or manumission in closure." (38)

Evidence: If the obsession of the troubled person is in divorce, then if it becomes firm and controls him, it leads him to inflict divorce involuntarily without intending it, and that he utters it so as to become comfortable with what he is suffering, so it is due to the power of the motive and the lack of impediment, so his divorce does not count even if it is uttered unless intended. (39)

It is not just speaking the word divorce necessitates its counting; rather, there must be an intent and a will behind uttering the word “divorce” thereof. (40)

Evidence for the second opinion:

Those who claim that the divorce of the obsessed person counts invoked evidence, including:

1- Divorce of the obsessed person is obligated as it is in its context that he owns, because if he rationalized divorce, so he is qualified to cause divorce, so his divorce is issued by his will and in its context.

This evidence is discussed: that the state of the person with obsessive-compulsive disorder is severer than that of the compelled person because he is deprived of the will and intent due to the predominance of obsession.

Most correct opinion:

The most correct opinion on this issue - and Allah knows best - is that the divorce of the obsessed person does not count; even if he uttered it unless it was intended by him, because he uttered the divorce because of the severity of his condition; so he is forced to do so (42) Also, the non-counting of divorce by the obsessed person is in accordance with the principles and rules of Sharia. As Allah, the Almighty says: 'Allah does not burden a soul beyond its capacity' (43)

Second: Divorce of the person with psychotic disorder:

If the mentally disturbed person divorces while his perception is affected or eliminated, for instance, if he did that during a bout of schizophrenia, mania, or a bout of severe and chronic depression, does his divorce count during such disorders that affect his awareness?

If the person with disturbed psychotic disorder loses his awareness - and this is most of his condition - the ruling on his divorce is the same as the ruling on the insane person, so the divorce of the psychotic patient does not count if it was unintentional, based on the agreement of the jurists on the invalidity of the divorce of the insane. (44)

They cited the following evidence:

1- The Traditional Hadith narrated by Aisha (may Allah be pleased with her), She said: The Messenger of Allah (May peace be upon him) said: “There is no divorce or manumission (release) in the case of closure.” (45)

Aspect of evidence: The closure deals with everything that is closed to the path of his intention, and his perception thereof, such as the drunkard person, the insane person, the compelled person, the angry person, and the divorce counts only on uttering it on purpose and a perception of what he intends, and the condition of the previously said people is a state of closure, so their divorce does not count. The same applies to the psychotic disordered person because he is in the judgment of the insane person. (46)

2- An analogy with a sale, just as it is not valid to sell by an insane person, his divorce is not valid too due to the fact that both of them are an act that removes property thereof. (47)

Results of the research:

The researcher concluded the following results:

1- Islamic legislation preceded the entire legislations whether old or modern ones by clarifying the provisions of the marriage of the psychologically disturbed people.

2 - Islamic legislation is characterized by ease and removal of embarrassment from people, no matter how minimal it is, and that Allah, the Almighty removes the burden from people who are inflicted with the least disease.

3- The marriage of the psychologically disturbed person is permissible, provided that he is married off by his guardian, and that his fiancée is aware of his disease before marriage and after the doctor supervising his condition decides the possibility of his marriage.

4- Divorce of the obsessive person does not count, even if he uttered it according to the opinions of the majority of the Muslim jurists “fuqaha”.

5- If the psychotic person loses his awareness, the ruling on his divorce is the same as the ruling on the divorce of the insane person, and it does not count.

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